

Utilization of Anthracene-Functionalized Poly(2-oxazolines) as a Dispersant of Carbon Black in Water and Dodecane

Zivani Varanaraja, Roberto Terracciano, Nathan Hollingsworth, Ross Green, James Beament, and C. Remzi Becer*

Cite This: *Macromolecules* 2024, 57, 5769–5779

Read Online

ACCESS |

Metrics & More

Article Recommendations

Supporting Information

ABSTRACT: Poly(2-oxazoline)s (POxs) offer an unparalleled degree of functionalization in the fabrication of smart, functional polymers for a wide range of applications. By utilizing 2-ethyl-2-oxazoline and a unique hydrophobic 2-oxazoline monomer, 2-isostearyl-2-oxazoline, we report the synthesis of a library of functionalized poly(2-ethyl-2-oxazoline)s (PEtOxs) and poly(2-isostearyl-2-oxazoline)s (PiStOxs) that show incredible potential as dispersants of carbon black (CB) in water and dodecane. The initiation and termination of 2-oxazoline polymerizations by direct end-capping can be exploited to introduce a variety of end-groups. Herein, we utilize this methodology to report the efficient synthesis of anthracene-end-capped PEtOx and PiStOx. A small library of 9-(chloromethyl)anthracene-initiated polymers was also synthesized to increase the aromaticity to investigate its influence on the dispersion of CB. The solution behavior of the polymers in aqueous and nonaqueous media is studied via turbidity measurement, and their ability to disperse CB in water and dodecane systems is assessed by a UV–vis spectrophotometer. PEtOx and PiStOx both display characteristics of a good dispersant, and PiStOx exhibits better performance than a commercially available dispersant, presenting superior results than previously reported for POx.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon black (CB) is the material produced by incomplete thermal combustion or decomposition of hydrocarbons.¹ It has a high surface area-to-volume ratio and is widely used in a plethora of applications due to its excellent resistance to chemicals, light, and temperature.² Some of the common uses of CB are in rubber products, coatings and paints, plastics, and batteries.^{3–5} A recent review by Andrioli et al.⁶ highlights the current scientific importance of CB in renewable energy harvesting and environmental remediation. CB and functionalized CB materials have been proven to be essential and competitive against other carbon nanomaterials for supercapacitors, CO₂ separations, and batteries and as catalyst support in solar and fuel cells.^{7–16} In addition, CB is the largest industrially produced nanocarbon with a projected annual manufacture of 15 Mt by 2025.⁶

However, one of the challenges is that CB is poorly soluble in aqueous media and most organic solvents.^{17–19} This is primarily due to the formation of aggregates because of the high surface free energy, large specific surface area, and strong van der Waals forces.^{6,20} Therefore, there is considerable attention paid to studying the surface chemistry of CB to increase its colloidal stability so that its handling and processability for a broad spectrum of applications can be improved. One method to solve this problem is to use chemical oxidation processes that could introduce functional groups onto the surface of the CB particles

to improve interaction between the solvent particles and CB; this would then reduce the aggregation of particles.²¹ The disadvantage of this is that the covalent modification of CB could modify the intrinsic properties of the nanocarbon, such as decrease the conductivity and/or mechanical toughness. To overcome this issue, the use of noncovalent additives such as dispersants can decrease the surface tension and increase the dispersion of CB in a solvent without altering the properties of the nanoparticle.²²

Dispersion of carbonized materials usually occurs through enthalpy-driven interactions, such as π – π between the nanocarbon surface and the dispersant and/or entropy-driven interactions.^{23–25} Dynamic dispersion happens when the dispersant surrounds the nanoparticle through adsorption and prevents clumping. In contrast, static dispersion is the multipoint interaction between the surface of the CB and polymer dispersant, resulting in the polymer wrapping around the particles and blocking aggregation. Some commonly used dispersants of carbonized materials include sodium dodecyl

Received: April 13, 2024

Revised: May 26, 2024

Accepted: June 3, 2024

Published: June 10, 2024

Scheme 1. Synthesis of Poly(2-ethyl-2-oxazoline)s and Poly(2-isostearyl-2-oxazoline)s via Cationic Ring-Opening Polymerization^a

^aP1–P10 are obtained by direct end-capping after CROP with 9-anthracenecarboxylic acid (AnCOOH). P11–P15 are obtained by initiating with 9-(chloromethyl)anthracene and terminating with AnCOOH. P16 and P17 are obtained by initiating with the bisinitiator 1,4-bis(bromomethyl)benzene and end-capping with AnCOOH.

sulfate (SDS),^{26,27} Triton X,^{28,29} sodium dodecylbenzenesulfonate (SDBS),^{30,31} polyfluorene (PFO),²³ polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP)³², and Hypermer.³³ Most frequently investigated solvents are water, toluene, and NMP but dispersion of CB is desired in multiple solvents. Thus, there is ongoing need to synthesize polymer that can work in both aqueous and nonaqueous media to disperse CB.

Recently, a study found that poly(2-oxazoline)s (POxs) are a promising short-term dispersant of CB in dodecane.³⁴ POx is a class of polymers that have been gaining emerging attention in both industrial and biological applications due to their unparalleled synthetic versatility.^{35–39} Recent studies have consistently showcased their benefits in biological applications^{40–42}, but their potential in other uses is rarely explored. The incorporation of aromatic groups into the polymer is believed to increase affinity to nanocarbon and improve dispersion.⁴³ However, the functional dispersant must still be soluble in the solvent to disperse the CB effectively. Hence, a right balance of aromaticity needs to be applied while keeping the solubility high. POx is beneficial and can be utilized efficiently here as there are surfeit amount of research on their synthesis and characterization. Moreover, there are multiple ways to functionalize a POx chain: via the α -end by using a functional initiator, through the ω -end by using a functional chain terminator, and by a functional side chain.⁴⁴ Side chain functionalization can be obtained by either postpolymerization modification or by polymerizing a monomer containing the specific functionality. A variety of nucleophiles, such as amines, thiols, and carboxylic acids, can be used to terminate the POx chain, and the ability to further functionalize the α -chain end offers incredible flexibility and control on the physical and chemical properties of POx-based materials. In recent years, this methodology has been exploited for a range of studies and applications.^{45,46}

Herein, we utilize these accessible techniques to synthesize a library of POxs with varying degrees of polymerization and anthracene functionalization; this is conveyed via Scheme 1. Direct end-capping of 9-anthracenecarboxylic acid onto poly(2-ethyl-2-oxazoline) (PEtOx) and poly(2-isostearyl-2-oxazoline) (PiStOx) is demonstrated for the first time to the best of our knowledge. Furthermore, a functional initiator, 9-(chloromethyl)anthracene, is employed to increase the anthracene functionality. This has only been accomplished once before by Kempe et al. to showcase the synthesis of a versatile multifunctional POx scaffold.⁴⁷ In this study, the solution behavior of the polymers in aqueous and nonaqueous media is investigated via turbidity measurement, and their ability to disperse CB in water and dodecane is assessed. PEtOx and PiStOx both display characteristics of a good dispersant, and PiStOx exhibits better performance than a commercially available dispersant does, presenting superior results than previously reported for POx.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Materials. 2-Ethyl-2-oxazoline (99+%, Acros Organics) was dried over calcium hydride and distilled under reduced pressure prior to use. Methyl *p*-toluenesulfonate (98%, Aldrich, MeTos) was distilled under reduced pressure. The extra dry solvent acetonitrile (99.8%, MeCN) and dichloromethane (99.8%) were purchased from Acros Organics and stored over molecular sieves and under inert atmosphere. 9-Anthracenylmethyl chloride (>98%, AnCl) was purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., and 1,4-bis(bromomethyl)benzene (>97%, Br–Bn–Br) and sodium iodide (>99%, NaI) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. *N,N*-Diisopropylethylamine (>99%, DIPEA) and 9-anthracenecarboxylic acid (>99%, AnCOOH) were purchased from Scientific Laboratory Supplies Ltd. and used as received. 2-Isostearyl-2-oxazoline (iStOx) was provided by Infineum UK Ltd. and distilled under reduced pressure prior to use. Triton X-100 (TX) was purchased by Sigma-Aldrich, and Hypermer B246 was provided by Croda. Carbon Black VULCAN XC72R (CB) was purchased from James M. Brown Ltd. and used as received.

Table 1. Data of the Synthesized PO_x via CROP, Initiated with Methyl *p*-toluenesulfonate (MeTos), 9-(Chloromethyl)anthracene (AnCl), or 1,4-Bis(bromomethyl)benzene (Br–Bn–Br) at 100 °C and Terminated with AnCOOH^a

code	polymer	initiator	DP	total conv (%)	M _{n,theo} (g mol ⁻¹)	M _{n,GPC} (g mol ⁻¹)	Đ	IEE (%)
P _a	PEtOx ₆₀	MeTos	60	100	6160	6380	1.11	
P ₁	PEtOx ₇ -An		7	100	930	860	1.11	99
P ₂	PEtOx ₃₀ -An		30	100	3200	2522	1.09	96
P ₃	PEtOx ₅₄ -An		54	100	5680	4390	1.21	87
P ₄	PEtOx ₁₀₅ -An		105	100	7670	6150	1.22	92
P ₅	PEtOx ₁₂₀ -An		120	100	11,130	9400	1.18	84
P _b	PiStOx ₁₂	MeTos	12	100	3720	3250	1.12	
P ₆	PiStOx ₁₅ -An		15	98	4630	3890	1.16	99
P ₇	PiStOx ₅₁ -An		51	94	9890	8450	1.11	95
P ₈	PiStOx ₈₉ -An		89	96	18,230	13,150	1.12	86
P ₉	PiStOx ₁₀₀ -An		100	99	25,960	13,180	1.26	72
P ₁₀	PiStOx ₁₅₅ -An		155	98	43,260	22,580	1.20	69
P ₁₁	An-PEtOx ₂₆ -An	AnCl	26	100	2800	2330	1.16	
P ₁₂	An-PEtOx ₄₇ -An		47	100	4590	3300	1.11	
P ₁₃	An-PiStOx ₂₄ -An	AnCl	24	59	7830	5020	1.33	
P ₁₄	An-PiStOx ₄₈ -An		48	56	14,660	7100	1.32	
P ₁₅	An-PiStOx ₁₀₃ -An		103	96	30,970	12,350	1.32	
P ₁₆	An-PEtOx-Bn-PEtOx-An	Br–Bn–Br	34	100	3920	3220	1.28	95
P ₁₇	An-PiStOx-Bn-PiStOx-An		30	99	9820	7680	1.14	93

^aIEE is the implied end-capping efficiency.

Synthetic Procedures for the Preparation of Polymers.

Synthesis of Homopolymers P₁–P₁₀. The polymerizations were performed with an initial monomer concentration of 4 M in acetonitrile with varying monomer-to-initiator ratios using MeTos as the initiator. As an example, P₁ was synthesized as follows. EtOx (1.00g, 10.09 mmol), MeTos (0.27g, 1.44 mmol), and MeCN (1.50 mL) were transferred into a sealed microwave vial equipped with a magnetic stirrer bar. The microwave vial was preheated and sealed before transfer to remove any contamination and water. After transfer, the reaction mixture was purged with nitrogen for 30 min. A small aliquot was taken to calculate [M]:[I] via ¹H NMR. Subsequently, the reaction mixture was reacted for the desired time at 100 °C in the oil bath. Upon completion, a relief needle was inserted into the seal to release the pressure, and 5 equiv of AnCOOH and DIPEA dissolved in minimal MeCN was added to terminate the reaction. The reaction mixture was left to stir for 16 h at 60 °C. P₁–P₅ reaction mixtures were precipitated twice in cold ether, filtered, and dried to obtain the purified product. P₆–P₁₀ reaction mixtures were precipitated twice in cold methanol, filtered, and dried to obtain the purified product.

Synthesis of Homopolymers P₁₁–P₁₆. The polymerizations were performed with an initial monomer concentration of 4 M in acetonitrile with varying monomer-to-initiator ratios using MeTos as the initiator. As an example, P₁₁ was synthesized as follows. EtOx (1.00g, 10.09 mmol), AnCl (91.48 mg, 0.40 mmol), NaI (59.96 mg, 0.40 mmol), and MeCN (1.50 mL) were transferred into a sealed microwave vial equipped with a magnetic stirrer bar. The microwave vial was preheated and sealed before transfer to remove any contamination and water. After transfer, the reaction mixture was purged with nitrogen for 30 min. A small aliquot was taken to calculate [M]:[I] via ¹H NMR. Subsequently, the reaction mixture was reacted for the desired time at 100 °C in the oil bath. Upon completion, a relief needle was inserted into the seal to release the pressure, and 5 equiv of AnCOOH and DIPEA dissolved in minimal MeCN was added to terminate the reaction. The reaction mixture was left to stir for 16 h at 60 °C. P₁₁–P₁₃ reaction mixtures were precipitated twice in cold ether, filtered, and dried to obtain the purified product. P₁₅ and P₁₆ reaction mixtures were precipitated twice in cold methanol, filtered, and dried to obtain the purified product.

Synthesis of Homopolymers P₁₇ and P₁₈. The polymerizations were performed with an initial monomer concentration of 4 M in acetonitrile with varying monomer-to-initiator ratios using MeTos as the initiator. As an example, P₁₇ was synthesized as follows: EtOx

(1.00g, 10.09 mmol), 1,4-bis(bromomethyl)benzene (88.69 mg, 0.336 mmol), and MeCN (1.50 mL) were transferred into a sealed microwave vial equipped with a magnetic stirrer bar. The microwave vial was preheated and sealed before transfer to remove any contamination and water. After transfer, the reaction mixture was purged with nitrogen for 30 min. A small aliquot was taken to calculate [M]:[I] via ¹H NMR. Subsequently, the reaction mixture was reacted for the desired time at 100 °C in oil bath. Upon completion, a relief needle was inserted into the seal to release the pressure, and 5 equiv of AnCOOH and DIPEA dissolved in minimal MeCN was added to terminate the reaction. The reaction mixture was left to stir for 16 h at 60 °C. The P₁₇ reaction mixture was precipitated twice in cold ether, filtered, and dried to obtain the purified product. The P₁₈ reaction mixture was precipitated twice in cold methanol, filtered, and dried to obtain the purified product.

Instrumentation. Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (¹H NMR). All spectra were recorded on Bruker Avance III HD 300 and III HD 400 MHz. CDCl₃ was used as solvent, and the signal of the residual CHCl₃ served as reference for the chemical shift, δ. The data analysis was performed by using SpinWorks Java software.

Gel Permeation Chromatography (GPC). The measurements were performed by using THF with 2% TEA as the eluent. The Agilent Technologies 1260 Infinity instrument was equipped with refractive index (RI) and 308 nm UV detectors, a PLgel 5 μm guard column, and a PLgel 5 μm mixed D column (300 × 7.5 mm). Samples were run at 1 mL min⁻¹ at 40 °C. Poly(methyl methacrylate) standards (Agilent PMMA calibration kits, M-M-10 and M-L-10) were used for the calibration. Before injection (100 μL), the samples were filtered through a PTFE membrane with a 0.2 μL pore size. The data was determined by conventional calibration using Agilent GPC/SEC software and plotted in OriginPro 2022b.

Matrix-Assisted Laser Desorption Ionization Time-of-Flight Mass Spectrometry (MALDI-TOF). All MALDI-TOF was performed on a Bruker Autoflex Speed mass spectrometer using a nitrogen laser delivering 2 ns pulses at 337 nm with positive ion ToF detection performed using an accelerating voltage of 25 kV. The matrix used was trans-2-[3-(4-tertbutylphenyl)-2-methyl-2-propylidene] malonitrile (DCTB) dissolved in THF and sodium trifluoroacetate used as an S2 cationic agent (solution in ethanol). Samples were measured in reflective mode and calibrated against poly(methyl methacrylate) standards. Data analysis was then performed with Brukerflex Analysis software.

Figure 1. (A1) GPC traces of compounds **P1–P5**. The dotted traces show PEtOx before end-capping, and the solid line indicates after termination with AnCOOH. Measurements were performed using THF (2% TEA and 0.01% BHT) as the eluent. (A2) Exemplar ¹H NMR spectrum of **P2** measured in CDCl₃ after purification. (B1) GPC traces of **P6–P10** after end-capping with AnCOOH. Measurements were performed using THF (2% TEA and 0.01% BHT) as the eluent. (B2) Exemplar ¹H NMR spectrum of **P6** measured in CDCl₃ after purification.

Figure 2. Full spectrum and magnified inset (dashed box) of MALDI-TOF for **P2**. Calculated $m/z + \text{Na}$ is 2541.6581, and measured $m/z + \text{Na}$ is 2541.652; a difference of 0.0061 is observed. Thus, the primary distribution corresponds to the sodium adduct of the completely functionalized product.

UV-vis and Turbidity Measurements. An Agilent Technologies Cary 100 UV-vis spectrophotometer equipped with an Agilent Technologies Cary temperature controller and an Agilent Technologies 6 × 6 multicell block Peltier was used to obtain absorbance and for the turbidity analyses for determining the transition temperature of each sample. The measurements were performed using the Suprasil quartz cuvettes (Hellman, 100-QS, light path of 10.00 mm) or a disposable cuvette (UV grade PMMA) filled with 5 mg mL⁻¹ solutions of each polymer in dodecane and water. The absorbance of each polymer solution was measured from 200 to 800 nm. Turbidity analysis involved two heating and cooling cycles between 10 and 85 °C being performed with a temperature gradient of 1 °C min⁻¹ at $\lambda = 500$ nm for

each sample. All of the data was obtained using the Cary WinUV software and plotted using the OriginPro 2021b.

Dispersion Measurements. An Agilent Technologies Cary 100 UV-vis spectrophotometer equipped with an Agilent Technologies Cary temperature controller and an Agilent Technologies 6 × 6 multicell block Peltier was used for the dispersion measurements of each sample. The measurements were performed using Suprasil quartz cuvettes (Hellman, 100-QS, light path of 10.00 mm) or a disposable cuvette (UV grade PMMA) filled with 0.05 mg mL⁻¹ of CB and 3 mg mL⁻¹ of each polymer in dodecane and water. The solutions were then subjected to an hourly UV scan at a wavelength of 500 nm for 16 h to measure absorbance. Following this, the stability of the dispersions was studied for 7 days with a scan every 24 h.

Figure 3. (A) GPC traces of P11–P12. (B) GPC traces of P13–P15. (C) GPC traces of P16 and P17. The dotted traces show the polymer before end-capping, and the solid line represents the polymer after termination with AnCOOH. All GPC measurements were performed using THF (2% TEA and 0.01% BHT) as the eluent. (D) Turbidity curves of the second heating and cooling cycle of polymer solution in water ($C = 5 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$) measured at $\lambda = 500 \text{ nm}$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Synthesis and Analysis of Polymers. Although the CROP of EtOx has been extensively studied, the research into the polymerization of soy-based oxazolines is small,^{48,49} and the CROP of iStOx has not been previously reported to the best of our knowledge. The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR of iStOx is provided via Figure S1. These homopolymers were specifically chosen as PEtOx and PiStOx are soluble in water and dodecane, respectively, and the aim of the study was to obtain an effective dispersant for both aqueous and nonaqueous systems. The synthesis of PEtOx and PiStOx with varying monomer-to-initiator ratios was conducted at 100°C to facilitate immediate end-capping postpolymerization, and the reactions are summarized via Table 1. The polymers were all terminated with 9-anthracenecarboxylic acid in excess. A quantitative overall monomer conversion was determined for all of the polymers from the ^1H NMR analysis. The CROP yielded well-defined homopolymers with low-dispersity values between 1.09 and 1.33. As reflected in Table 1, the experimental M_n values are lower than the theoretical values for all of the polymers. However, this was expected as the PMMA standards used for the

GPC calibration have a different hydrodynamic volume in comparison to POx. The GPC traces of polymers P1–P10 are shown via Figure 1, and the traces of polymers P11–P17 are displayed in Figure 3A–C. A GPC sample was obtained prior to end-capping for P1–P5, and this is shown as the dotted line in Figure 1A1; however, this was not possible for P6–P17 as the polymer solutions were too viscous, and hence, it was difficult to take a sample from before functionalization. Some high-molecular-weight shoulders are detected on the GPC, particularly for P5 and P10. This is likely due to the occurrence of chain transfer reactions, followed by chain coupling at high monomer conversions. This is more prevalent in higher degree of polymerization (DP) polymers and has been previously reported by various research groups.^{50–52}

Homopolymers P1–P10 all reached $\geq 94\%$ monomer conversion, and the ^1H NMR spectroscopic analysis indicated successful functionalization of PEtOx and PiStOx with anthracene after purification due to the appearance of the aromatic peaks at 7.4–8.5 ppm. The development of the methylene peaks at 4.75 and 3.80 ppm further supports the occurrence of effective end-capping; this is shown via Figure 1

for **P2** and **P6**. The NMR spectra for the rest of the polymers are represented in Figure S2. The spectra were used to determine the functionalization efficiency of each polymer. The implied functionalization efficiency of polymers **P1–P5** was calculated by comparing the ratio of the integrals between the aromatic protons of the anthracene (8 ppm) and the $-\text{CH}_3$ group of the PEtOx (1.10–1.20 ppm). The implied functionalization efficiency of polymers **P6–P10** was calculated by comparing the ratio of the integrals between the aromatic protons of the anthracene (8 ppm) and the $-\text{CH}_2$ group of the PiStOx (2.23 ppm). Polymers **P1–P5** all demonstrated >80% end-capping efficiency, and polymers **P6–P10** indicated >68% end-capping efficiency. In general, it can be observed that increasing the DP leads to a reduction in end-capping efficiency. This is consistent with literature, and it could be due to increased shielding of the end-group by the polymer chain in the solution, leading to a reduced accessibility for the nucleophilic attack by the carboxylic acid.⁴⁵ However, even at a DP above 100, NMR analysis demonstrated an achievement of over 65% functionality for all polymers.

Moreover, further end-group analysis of **P1** and **P2** by MALDI-TOF spectrometry revealed greater functionalization compared to NMR; a recent study found a similar observation where MALDI analysis disclosed the presence of only the end-capped product, indicating higher functionalization efficiency compared to NMR analysis.⁴⁶ The MALDI analyses of **P1** and **P2**, shown via Figure 2 and Figure S3, both displayed a primary distribution that matched closely with the calculated molecular weight, with an average repeating unit of 99.1, which is identical to the molecular weight of the EtOx monomer repeating unit. Verification of the end-groups was conducted by comparing the calculated and found masses of an individual *n*-mer. Taking **P1** as an example, the theoretical mass of the sodium adduct of the functionalized 7-mer end-capped with AnCOOH is 952.5 Da. The observed mass by MALDI for the 7-mer is 952.3 Da; a difference of only 0.2 Da is observed. MALDI-TOF spectrometry analysis was also attempted on **P3–P6**, but no clear spectrum could be obtained under various sample preparation methods for higher DP polymers; this was particularly difficult for PiStOx polymers as they do not ionize well.

¹H NMR analysis of **P11–P17** is shown via Figures S6–S8, and the development of the aromatic peaks at 7–9 ppm and the methylene peaks at 4.75 and 3.80 ppm again reveal effective functionalization. An overall implied functionalization efficiency of **P16** and **P17** is calculated in a similar method to **P1–P10**; this time, it is assumed that each polymer end is end-capped uniformly. However, the end-capping efficiency of **P11–P15** could not be accurately calculated via NMR due to the overlapping of the anthracene peaks from the α -end and ω -end. Nevertheless, to further clarify the increased confidence of successful functionalization and confirm the presence of the anthracene group, UV-vis spectrophotometer was utilized to examine the purified polymers. The UV spectroscopy scans of polymers **P1–P10** are shown via Figure S4, and the scans of polymers **P11–P17** are displayed in Figure S9. As the anthracene group is UV active and typically has four unique absorption bands between 328 and 395,^{53,54} the analysis could easily indicate if the polymers have been successfully initiated and end-capped. All UV evaluations of PEtOx functionalized polymers were conducted in water, and all UV analyses of PiStOx polymers were conducted in dodecane. As shown in Figures S4 and S9, the UV scans of all the purified polymers have distinctive absorption peaks at 330, 347, 365, and 385, strongly

indicating the presence of the anthracene functional group and successful end-capping. As expected, at the same concentration, absorbance at each wavelength decreased with increasing DP.

The effect of the polymer composition on their solution behavior in nonaqueous and aqueous media was evaluated via turbidity measurements; the solvents tested were dodecane for iStOx-based polymers and water for EtOx-based polymers. Thus, 5 mg mL⁻¹ solutions in each solvent were prepared and subjected to two heating/cooling cycles from 10 to 80 °C at a wavelength of 500 nm using an UV-Vis spectrophotometer. It is worth noting that the anthracene carboxylic acid on its own is insoluble in both of these solvents. In comparison, at room temperature, all the functionalized polymers, apart from **P1**, had >90% solubility. Figure S5 shows that the second heating and cooling cycles of **P1–P10** and **P1** reached 0% transmittance at ~70 °C but were only partially soluble with 38% transmittance at room temperature. All of the other monofunctionalized homopolymers **P2–P10** were not thermoresponsive and had >90% transmittance at all temperatures.

In contrast, the bifunctionalized polymers **P11**, **P12**, and **P16** exhibit a lower critical solution temperature (LCST) in water; this is demonstrated via Figure 3D. Polymers that have an LCST experience an entropy-driven change in conformation in the solution that is temperature induced.^{55,56} Therefore, they will be miscible in solution below the critical temperature but will become immiscible or partially immiscible above the critical temperature. Some POxs, such as PEtOx and PPrOx, are known to display LCST in water.⁵⁷ However, POxs with longer alkyl chains are too hydrophobic and do not dissolve in water. Instead, there has been recent reports of them exhibiting UCST-type behavior in nonaqueous solvents.⁴⁹ The LCST and UCST of a polymer in a solution is dependent on and can be modified by the composition, DP, dispersity, solvent, and branching. For example, it is known in literature that relatively short linear PEtOx (DP < 100) does not have an LCST below 100 °C in water and the lowest reported cloud point temperature (T_{CP}) was 66 °C when the DP was 500.⁵⁵ Adding a secondary hydrophobic monomer in the polymer chain can lower the LCST; this has been demonstrated previously by Hoogenboom et al.⁵⁸

In this study, an LCST for a PEtOx with a DP as low as 27 (**P11**) is observed by just incorporating two anthracene groups onto the polymer chain via the alpha (α) and omega (ω) termini. Polymers **P11**, **P12**, and **P16** have a T_{CP} of 38, 44, and 33 °C, respectively, which are considerably lower than the previously reported LCST values of PEtOx homopolymers. However, there is hysteresis present, and this is likely due to the difference in the formation of intramolecular hydrogen bonds in the collapsed state.⁵⁹ **P16** does not fully reach 0% transmittance, indicating that the polymer is only partially immiscible at 80 °C. Increasing the DP of the polymers increases the LCST due to greater hydrogen bonding with water and the presence of the hydrophobic anthracene having a lower impact. None of the other polymers investigated showed any thermoresponsive behavior in water or dodecane; this is shown through Figures S5 and S10. Bifunctionalized PiStOx polymers **P13–P15** and **P17** were all soluble and had above 95% transmittance in dodecane at all the temperatures tested.

Application as a Dispersant for Carbon Black. Following the synthesis and analysis, the polymers were tested as dispersants for CB. All dispersion investigations of PEtOx functionalized polymers were conducted in water, and all dispersion studies of PiStOx polymers were conducted in

Figure 4. (A1) Absorbance of the polymers (3 mg/mL) with CB (0.05 mg/mL) in water at $\lambda = 500$ nm for 7 days. (B1) Absorbance of the polymers (3 mg/mL) with CB (0.05 mg/mL) in dodecane at $\lambda = 500$ nm for 7 days. (A2) Visual observation on day 7 of P4, P5, and P3 in water in the order of increasing absorbance and dispersion compared to the reference cuvette with only solvent (R) and the NP cuvette. (B2) Visual observation on day 7 of P15, P9, and P17 in dodecane in the order of increasing absorbance and dispersion compared to the reference cuvette with R and the NP cuvette.

Table 2. Data of the Absorbance and Dispersion of CB in Water and Dodecane with the Synthesized POx^a

code	solvent	absorbance (day 0)	app CB conc (day 0, mg/mL)	relative performance (day 0, %)	absorbance (day 7)	app CB conc (day 7, mg/mL)	relative performance (day 7, %)
NP	water	0.33	0.010	20	0	0	0
Pa		0.90	0.028	56	0.18	0.006	11
P2		0.99	0.031	61	0.29	0.009	18
P3		1.82	0.056	111	0.88	0.027	54
P4		1.27	0.039	78	0.40	0.013	25
P5		1.27	0.039	78	0.62	0.019	38
P11		0.62	0.019	38	0.01	0	0
P12		0.61	0.019	37	0.01	0	0
P16		0.74	0.023	45	0.02	0	1
NP	dodecane	0.25	0.021	42	0.19	0.016	31
Pb		0.99	0.084	167	0.35	0.029	59
P6		1.24	0.104	209	0.75	0.063	126
P7		1.26	0.106	213	0.06	0.005	10
P8		1.18	0.099	198	0.66	0.056	111
P9		1.47	0.124	247	0.87	0.073	146
P10		1.15	0.097	193	0.54	0.046	91
P13		1.26	0.107	213	0.02	0.002	3
P14		1.73	0.147	293	0	0	0
P15		1.53	0.129	259	0.81	0.069	137
P17		1.52	0.129	257	1.13	0.096	191

^aApparent (app) CB concentration (conc) and performance are calculated with respect to Triton X-100 in water and with respect to Hypermer B246 in dodecane.

dodecane. P1 was the only polymer that was discarded from testing, and this was because it had a very low solubility in water. Evaluation of dispersion consisted of making a stock solution of CB in each solvent at a concentration of 0.05 mg/mL. This concentration was chosen after testing two commercially

available dispersants: TX in an aqueous system and Hypermer B246 in a nonaqueous system; different concentrations of CB were tested, and the calibration line is displayed via Figure S11. A 3 mL portion of the stock solution and 9 mg of the polymer being tested were then added to a vial. A reference vial was made

with 3 mL of the stock solution only and no polymer (NP). This was used as the control against which to compare the other vials against. The solutions containing 0.05 mg mL⁻¹ CB and 3 mg mL⁻¹ polymer were then subjected to an hourly UV scan at a wavelength of 500 nm for 16 h. Following this, the stability of the dispersions was studied for 7 days, with a scan being conducted once a day; this is demonstrated through Figure 4. A magnified inset of the first 14 h is presented in Figure S12. Similar methods have been previously employed to examine dispersions of CB and carbon nanotubes.^{28,60,61}

The absorbance values were then used to compare against the dispersants TX and Hypermer B246 (HP) in water and dodecane, respectively, to analyze performance. At 0.05 mg/mL CB concentration, TX had an absorbance of 1.63 in water and HP had an absorbance of 0.59. Using this, the implied concentration and efficiency of the synthesized polymers was calculated. For example, on day 0, P2 had an absorbance of 0.99, indicating it was dispersing 61% of CB relative to TX, which translates to 0.031 mg/mL of CB. This then drops to an absorbance of 0.29 on day 7, representing a dispersion performance of 18% relative to TX. Similarly, PiStOx-based polymers were compared against the absorbance value of HP to calculate the relative efficiency and concentration. The performance of all the synthesized polymers is summarized in Table 2.

The efficiency of the water-soluble polymers P2–P5, P11, P12, and P16 as dispersants of CB was examined first. As seen in Figure 4A1, P3 had the greatest absorbance from day 0 and was the only polymer to give an absorbance value greater than TX initially. This suggests that the solution was more opaque, leading to an increased absorbance and hence indicating that more of the CB is being dispersed in water. Less sediment was also observed on the bottom of the cuvette. The biggest decrease in absorbance and performance is observed in the first 24 h before the dispersion stabilizes, and the trace begins to plateau off. Although P3 initially disperses 111% CB relative to TX, this falls to only 53% efficiency on day 7. This may be because some of the polymers wrapping around the CB particles become undone, leading to an increase in the level of sedimentation. Nevertheless, it is evident that adding the polymers P2–P5 increases dispersion as the reference vial with no polymer reached almost 0 absorbance after day 1, implying 100% transmittance and sedimentation and no scattering of CB. Additionally, it is evident that incorporating an anthracene group influences dispersion as Pa, with no functionalization, did not perform as well, falling below all the monofunctionalized polymers by day 7. Interestingly, the polymers containing two anthracene groups (P11, P12, and P16) had almost no effect on the CB dispersion. Although some dispersion is observed on day 0, they all reach almost 100% transmittance and no dispersion by day 5. Overall, P3, P5, and P4 were the most efficient dispersants from the series and a visual representation is shown through Figure 4A2 on day 7.

In comparison, the efficiency of PiStOx-based polymers P6–P10, P13–P15, and P17 as a dispersant of CB in dodecane was excellent and in some cases better than the commercially available HP. As shown on Table 2, all the functionalized polymers showed enhanced dispersion performance than HP did on day 0. It is also worth observing that NP absorbance in dodecane was not as low as that in water, showing that small amounts of CB can be dispersed in dodecane without any dispersants. This is probably because CB is very hydrophobic. In comparison to the aqueous system, the decrease in the absorbance in the first 24 h before stabilization of the dispersion

is much smaller, demonstrating greater consistency and efficiency. By day 7, five out of the seven functionalized polymers (P6, P8, P9, P15, and P17) still had a higher absorbance and hence dispersion relative to HP. Although the nonfunctionalized polymer, Pb, was a good dispersant in the beginning, it dropped below HP absorbance by day 2. Similar to PEtOx polymers, this could signify that the incorporation of the anthracene groups in PiStOx increases the affinity to CB and hence leads to a more stable wrapping mechanism and dispersion. From the monofunctionalized series, P9 had the best performance, dispersing 46% more CB than HP by day 7.

In contrast to the aqueous system, increasing the number of anthracene groups led to a greater dispersion efficiency in dodecane. This supports the earlier theory that aromatic groups are able to stabilize the CB in the solution via an augmented attraction and wrapping. As seen in Figure 4B1, P17 had the greatest absorbance from day 1 to day 7, dispersing nearly twice as much CB as HP in dodecane; the polymer dispersed 191% CB relative to HP. Although P14 initially had an absorbance of 1.74 on day 0 and the maximum dispersed CB, it had the largest decrease to nearly 0 absorbance by day 1, implying full sedimentation and no dispersion. This could be because the polymer chains wrap around the CB particle originally but become undone rapidly, leading to an increase in sediments. Interestingly, once the DP is increased from 48 to 103 (P15), the decrease in dispersion is reduced. This suggests that longer polymer chains are potentially more competent at surrounding the CB particles and increasing the dispersion efficiency via enhanced wrapping. Overall, P17, P9, and P15 were the most effective dispersants from the series and a visual representation of day 7 is shown through Figure 4B2. This study has expanded on the potential of POx as a dispersant in aqueous and nonaqueous medium for CB, demonstrating better dispersion strength in dodecane than previously published. In the future, it might be interesting to study the influence of altering the concentration and the polymer/CB ratio on dispersion efficiency. Additionally, it could be worth investigating the impact of different temperatures and how that could affect the dispersion mechanism. If intrigued, anthracene-initiated polymers before end-capping could also be analyzed. This may help compare anthracene from the initiator against anthracene introduced via termination to differentiate the functionalization and performance. Moreover, other aromatic groups, such as naphthalene, could be explored to assess if they exhibit superior dispersion capabilities. A challenge would be keeping the solubility high, particularly in aqueous solvents, as the aromaticity is increased. The solution behavior of the polymers could be further researched via other methods, such as DLS, to establish if they have interesting self-assembly that correlates to their dispersion abilities.

CONCLUSIONS

This study reports the efficient and fast functionalization of PEtOx and PiStOx via direct end-capping and utilization of functional initiators. The use of 9-anthracenecarboxylic acid to terminate POx is demonstrated for the first time to the best of our knowledge, and ¹NMR, GPC, MALDI, and UV–vis spectroscopy analyses indicate successful polymerization and functionalization. Moreover, the novel polymers' solution behavior in nonaqueous and aqueous systems was evaluated by turbidity measurements. An LCST-type phase transition is visible in water for three of the synthesized polymers (P11, P12, and P16). Following the synthesis, the polymers' ability as

dispersants of CB in water and dodecane was evaluated. The capability of PEtOx-based polymers as a dispersant is investigated for the first time in water, and P3 is shown to behave well as a short-term dispersant. In comparison, PiStOx polymers displayed excellent dispersions of CB in dodecane, delivering consistently enhanced performance in comparison to commercially available Hypermer 246 for 7 days. This expands previously reported research for POx and has shown a convenient and versatile method to vary the functionality to showcase the potential of this polymer class as a dispersant of carbonized materials in new applications.

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

SI Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.macromol.4c00843>.

NMR, MALDI-TOF, UV-vis, and carbon black dispersion data as well as supporting analysis of the polymers presented in the paper (PDF)

■ AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Author

C. Remzi Becer – Department of Chemistry, University of Warwick, Coventry CV4 7AL, United Kingdom; orcid.org/0000-0003-0968-6662; Email: remzi.becer@warwick.ac.uk

Authors

Zivani Varanaraja – Department of Chemistry, University of Warwick, Coventry CV4 7AL, United Kingdom

Roberto Terracciano – Department of Chemistry, University of Warwick, Coventry CV4 7AL, United Kingdom

Nathan Hollingsworth – Milton Hill Business & Technology Centre, Infineum UK Ltd., Abingdon, Oxfordshire OX13 6BB, United Kingdom

Ross Green – Milton Hill Business & Technology Centre, Infineum UK Ltd., Abingdon, Oxfordshire OX13 6BB, United Kingdom

James Beament – Milton Hill Business & Technology Centre, Infineum UK Ltd., Abingdon, Oxfordshire OX13 6BB, United Kingdom

Complete contact information is available at:

<https://pubs.acs.org/10.1021/acs.macromol.4c00843>

Author Contributions

Z.V. performed the experiments and analyzed the results. R.T. conducted the MALDI-TOF of P1 and reviewed the manuscript. N.H., R.G., J.B., and C.R.B. supervised the project.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

■ ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research was sponsored by Infineum UK and the University of Warwick.

■ REFERENCES

- (1) Jiang, S.; Bai, J.; Ying, X.; Han, J.; Zhu, K.; Mao, L. Synthesis and performance investigation of carbon black hyperdispersant IMD. *Journal of Coatings Technology and Research* **2023**, *20* (5), 1529–1539.
- (2) Heo, Y.-J.; Park, M.; Kang, W.-S.; Rhee, K. Y.; Park, S.-J. Preparation and characterization of carbon black/pitch-based carbon fiber paper composites for gas diffusion layers. *Composites Part B: Engineering* **2019**, *159*, 362–368.
- (3) Loganathan, K.; Bose, D.; Weinkauff, D. Surface modification of carbon black by nitrogen and allylamine plasma treatment for fuel cell electrocatalyst. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* **2014**, *39* (28), 15766–15771.
- (4) Lee, J.; Bae, J.; Kim, W.; Lee, S. A Study on Aqueous Dispersing of Carbon Black Nanoparticles Surface-Coated with Styrene Maleic Acid (SMA) Copolymer. *Polymers* **2022**, *14* (24), 5455 DOI: [10.3390/polym14245455](https://doi.org/10.3390/polym14245455).
- (5) Huang, M.; Tunncliffe, L. B.; Zhuang, J.; Ren, W.; Yan, H.; Busfield, J. J. C. Strain-Dependent Dielectric Behavior of Carbon Black Reinforced Natural Rubber. *Macromolecules* **2016**, *49* (6), 2339–2347.
- (6) Khodabakhshi, S.; Fulvio, P. F.; Andreoli, E. Carbon black reborn: Structure and chemistry for renewable energy harnessing. *Carbon* **2020**, *162*, 604–649.
- (7) Dicks, A. L. The role of carbon in fuel cells. *J. Power Sources* **2006**, *156* (2), 128–141.
- (8) Carmo, M.; Linardi, M.; Rochapoco, J. H₂O₂ treated carbon black as electrocatalyst support for polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cell applications. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* **2008**, *33* (21), 6289–6297.
- (9) Cheng, J.; Wang, L.; Huo, J.; Yu, H.; Yang, Q.; Deng, L. Study on synthesis of poly(N-isopropylacrylamide) grafted carbon black and temperature-dependence conductivity of grafted carbon black/epoxy composites. *J. Polym. Sci., Part B: Polym. Phys.* **2008**, *46* (15), 1529–1535.
- (10) Serov, A.; Kwak, C. Direct hydrazine fuel cells: A review. *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental* **2010**, *98* (1–2), 1–9.
- (11) Kwak, D.-H.; Lee, Y.-W.; Lee, K.-H.; Park, A.-R.; Moon, J.-S.; Park, K.-W. One-Step Synthesis of Hexapod Pt Nanoparticles Deposited on Carbon Black for Improved Methanol Electrooxidation. *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci.* **2013**, *8* (4), 5102–5107.
- (12) Li, X.; Li, X.; Banis, M. N.; Wang, B.; Lushington, A.; Cui, X.; Li, R.; Sham, T. K.; Sun, X. Tailoring interactions of carbon and sulfur in Li–S battery cathodes: significant effects of carbon–heteroatom bonds. *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2014**, *2* (32), 12866 DOI: [10.1039/c4ta02007c](https://doi.org/10.1039/c4ta02007c).
- (13) Trogadas, P.; Fuller, T. F.; Strasser, P. Carbon as catalyst and support for electrochemical energy conversion. *Carbon* **2014**, *75*, 5–42.
- (14) Zhang, B. B.; Chen, Y.; Wang, F.; Hong, R. Y. Surface modification of carbon black for the reinforcement of polycarbonate/acrylonitrile–butadiene–styrene blends. *Appl. Surf. Sci.* **2015**, *351*, 280–288.
- (15) Manthiram, A.; Fu, Y.; Chung, S. H.; Zu, C.; Su, Y. S. Rechargeable lithium-sulfur batteries. *Chem. Rev.* **2014**, *114* (23), 11751–87.
- (16) Li, J.; Fleetwood, J.; Hawley, W. B.; Kays, W. From Materials to Cell: State-of-the-Art and Prospective Technologies for Lithium-Ion Battery Electrode Processing. *Chem. Rev.* **2022**, *122* (1), 903–956.
- (17) Liu, T.; Jia, S.; Kowalewski, T.; Matyjaszewski, K.; Casado-Portilla, R.; Belmont, J. Water-Dispersible Carbon Black Nanocomposites Prepared by Surface-Initiated Atom Transfer Radical Polymerization in Protic Media. *Macromolecules* **2006**, *39* (2), 548–556.
- (18) Chen, S.; Qiu, L.; Cheng, H. M. Carbon-Based Fibers for Advanced Electrochemical Energy Storage Devices. *Chem. Rev.* **2020**, *120* (5), 2811–2878.
- (19) Growney, D. J.; Mykhaylyk, O. O.; Derouineau, T.; Fielding, L. A.; Smith, A. J.; Aragrag, N.; Lamb, G. D.; Armes, S. P. Star Diblock Copolymer Concentration Dictates the Degree of Dispersion of Carbon Black Particles in Nonpolar Media: Bridging Flocculation versus Steric Stabilization. *Macromolecules* **2015**, *48* (11), 3691–3704.
- (20) Griefel, D.; Huber, K.; Scherbauer, R.; Kwade, A. Dispersion kinetics of carbon black for the application in lithium-ion batteries. *Advanced Powder Technology* **2021**, *32* (7), 2280–2288.
- (21) Asokan, V.; Venkatachalapathy, V.; Rajavel, K.; Madsen, D. N. Microwave irradiation on carbon black: Studies on the transformation of particles into nano-balls, nano-sticks and nano-onion like structures. *J. Phys. Chem. Solids* **2016**, *99*, 173–181.
- (22) Fujigaya, T.; Nakashima, N. Non-covalent polymer wrapping of carbon nanotubes and the role of wrapped polymers as functional dispersants. *Sci. Technol. Adv. Mater.* **2015**, *16* (2), No. 024802.

- (23) Strano, M. S.; Moore, V. C.; Miller, M. K.; Allen, M. J.; Haroz, E. H.; Kittrell, C.; Hauge, R. H.; Smalley, R. E. The role of surfactant adsorption during ultrasonication in the dispersion of single-walled carbon nanotubes. *J. Nanosci Nanotechnol* **2003**, *3* (1–2), 81–6.
- (24) Kim, D.; Lee, T.; Kwon, M.; Paik, H. J.; Han, J. H.; Kang, M.; Choi, J.; Hong, S.; Kim, Y. A. Polymer wrapping-induced dispersion of single walled carbon nanotubes in ethylene glycol under mild sonication. *RSC Adv.* **2020**, *10* (44), 26262–26267.
- (25) Zhu, L.; Tian, X.; Pan, Y.; Chang, T.; Wang, K.; Niu, G.; Zhang, L.; Wang, C.; Han, W. Optimization of Serial Modular Continuous Mixing Process Parameters for Natural Rubber Composites Reinforced by Silica/Carbon Black. *Polymers* **2020**, *12* (2), 416 DOI: [10.3390/polym12020416](https://doi.org/10.3390/polym12020416).
- (26) Abdulhameed, A.; Halin, I. A.; Mohtar, M. N.; Hamidon, M. N. Optimization of Surfactant Concentration in Carbon Nanotube Solutions for Dielectrophoretic Ceiling Assembly and Alignment: Implications for Transparent Electronics. *ACS Omega* **2022**, *7* (4), 3680–3688.
- (27) Zhang, J.; Qi, Y.; Lv, T.; Niu, X.; Tai, B. Effects of sodium dodecyl sulfate on nano carbon black-filled cement paste: performance and microstructure. *Journal of Materials Research and Technology* **2023**, *24*, 1706–1715.
- (28) Sh, M. S.; Fard, F. G.; Khatibi, E.; Sarpoolaky, H. Dispersion and stability of carbon black nanoparticles, studied by ultraviolet–visible spectroscopy. *J. Taiwan Inst. Chem. Eng.* **2009**, *40* (5), S24–S27.
- (29) Zhang, Z.; Qu, C.; Zheng, T.; Lai, Y.; Li, J. Effect of Triton X-100 as Dispersant on Carbon Black for LiFePO₄ Cathode. *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci.* **2013**, *8* (5), 6722–6733.
- (30) Zhao, Y.; Lu, P.; Li, C.; Fan, X.; Wen, Q.; Zhan, Q.; Shu, X.; Xu, T.; Zeng, G. Adsorption mechanism of sodium dodecyl benzene sulfonate on carbon blacks by adsorption isotherm and zeta potential determinations. *Environ. Technol.* **2013**, *34* (1–4), 201–7.
- (31) Subramanian, S.; Øye, G. Aqueous carbon black dispersions stabilized by sodium lignosulfonates. *Colloid Polym. Sci.* **2021**, *299* (7), 1223–1236.
- (32) Xu, W.; Chen, H.; Li, H.; Wang, M. Fabrication of carbon black/crosslinked poly(vinyl pyrrolidone) core-shell nanoparticles stable in water. *Colloids Surf, A* **2005**, *266* (1–3), 68–72.
- (33) Yasin, S.; Luckham, P. F.; Iqbal, T.; Zafar, M.; Ramzan, N. Adsorption and Rheology of Graphitic Carbon Black Nonaqueous Dispersions Prepared Using Nonionic Surfactants. *J. Dispersion Sci. Technol.* **2013**, *34* (5), 737–746.
- (34) Varanaraja, Z.; Hollingsworth, N.; Green, R.; Becer, C. R. Poly(2-alkyl-2-oxazoline)-Based Copolymer Library with a Thermoresponsive Behavior in Dodecane. *ACS Applied Polymer Materials* **2023**, *5* (7), 5158–5168.
- (35) Hoogenboom, R. Poly(2-oxazoline)s: A Polymer Class with Numerous Potential Applications. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2009**, *48* (43), 7978–7994.
- (36) Sedlacek, O.; Monnery, B. D.; Filippov, S. K.; Hoogenboom, R.; Hruby, M. Poly(2-Oxazoline)s - Are They More Advantageous for Biomedical Applications Than Other Polymers? *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2012**, *33* (19), 1648–1662.
- (37) Verbraeken, B.; Monnery, B. D.; Lava, K.; Hoogenboom, R. The chemistry of poly(2-oxazoline)s. *Eur. Polym. J.* **2017**, *88*, 451–469.
- (38) Sedlacek, O.; Hoogenboom, R. Drug Delivery Systems Based on Poly(2-Oxazoline)s and Poly(2-Oxazine)s. *Adv. Ther.* **2020**, *3* (1), 1900168.
- (39) Glassner, M.; Vergaelen, M.; Hoogenboom, R. Poly(2-oxazoline)s: A comprehensive overview of polymer structures and their physical properties. *Polym. Int.* **2018**, *67* (1), 32–45.
- (40) Vinod, N.; Hwang, D.; Azam, S. H.; Van Swearingen, A. E. D.; Wayne, E.; Fussell, S. C.; Sokolsky-Papkov, M.; Pecot, C. V.; Kabanov, A. V. High-capacity poly(2-oxazoline) formulation of TLR 7/8agonist extends survival in a chemo-insensitive, metastatic model of lung adenocarcinoma. *Sci. Adv.* **2020**, *6* (25), No. eaba5542, DOI: [10.1126/sciadv.aba5542](https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aba5542).
- (41) Zhou, M.; Qian, Y.; Xie, J.; Zhang, W.; Jiang, W.; Xiao, X.; Chen, S.; Dai, C.; Cong, Z.; Ji, Z.; Shao, N.; Liu, L.; Wu, Y.; Liu, R. Poly(2-Oxazoline)-Based Functional Peptide Mimics: Eradicating MRSA Infections and Persister while Alleviating Antimicrobial Resistance. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.* **2020**, *59* (16), 6412–6419.
- (42) Zhou, M.; Liu, L.; Cong, Z.; Jiang, W.; Xiao, X.; Xie, J.; Luo, Z.; Chen, S.; Wu, Y.; Xue, X.; Shao, N.; Liu, R. A dual-targeting antifungal is effective against multidrug-resistant human fungal pathogens. *Nat. Microbiol.* **2024**, *9* (5), 1325–1339.
- (43) Nish, A.; Hwang, J. Y.; Doig, J.; Nicholas, R. J. Highly selective dispersion of single-walled carbon nanotubes using aromatic polymers. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2007**, *2* (10), 640–6.
- (44) Guillerm, B.; Monge, S.; Lapinte, V.; Robin, J. J. How to modulate the chemical structure of polyoxazolines by appropriate functionalization. *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2012**, *33* (19), 1600–12.
- (45) Podevyn, A.; Arys, K.; De la Rosa, V. R.; Glassner, M.; Hoogenboom, R. End-group functionalization of poly(2-oxazoline)s using methyl bromoacetate as initiator followed by direct amidation. *Eur. Polym. J.* **2019**, *120*, No. 109273, DOI: [10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2019.109273](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2019.109273).
- (46) Lefley, J.; Varanaraja, Z.; Drain, B.; Huband, S.; Beament, J.; Becer, C. R. Amphiphilic oligo(2-ethyl-2-oxazoline)s via straightforward synthesis and their self-assembly behaviour. *Polym. Chem.* **2023**, *14* (43), 4890–4897.
- (47) Kempe, K.; Hoogenboom, R.; Jaeger, M.; Schubert, U. S. Three-Fold Metal-Free Efficient (“Click”) Reactions onto a Multifunctional Poly(2-oxazoline) Designer Scaffold. *Macromolecules* **2011**, *44* (16), 6424–6432.
- (48) Hoogenboom, R.; Schubert, U. S. Microwave-assisted cationic ring-opening polymerization of a soy-based 2-oxazoline monomer. *Green Chem.* **2006**, *8*, 895 DOI: [10.1039/b600616g](https://doi.org/10.1039/b600616g).
- (49) Concilio, M.; Nguyen, N.; Becer, C. R. Oxazoline-Methacrylate Graft-Copolymers with Upper Critical Solution Temperature Behaviour in Yubase Oil. *Polym. Chem.* **2021**, *4359* DOI: [10.1039/d1py00534k](https://doi.org/10.1039/d1py00534k).
- (50) Litt, M.; Levy, A.; Herz, J. Polymerization of Cyclic Imino Ethers. X. Kinetics, Chain Transfer, and Repolymerization. *Journal of Macromolecular Science: Part A - Chemistry* **1975**, *9* (5), 703–727.
- (51) Hoogenboom, R.; Paulus, R. M.; Fijten, M. W. M.; Schubert, U. S. Concentration effects in the cationic ring-opening polymerization of 2-ethyl-2-oxazoline in N,N-dimethylacetamide. *J. Polym. Sci., Part A: Polym. Chem.* **2005**, *43* (7), 1487–1497.
- (52) Pinzner, F.; Keller, T.; Mut, J.; Bechold, J.; Seibel, J.; Groll, J. Polyoxazolines with a Vicinally Double-Bioactivated Terminus for Biomacromolecular Affinity Assessment. *Sensors* **2021**, *21* (9), 3153 DOI: [10.3390/s21093153](https://doi.org/10.3390/s21093153).
- (53) Filpponen, I.; Sadeghifar, H.; Argyropoulos, D. S. Photoresponsive Cellulose Nanocrystals. *Nanomater. Nanotechnol.* **2011**, *1* (1), 34–43.
- (54) Jones, R. N. The ultraviolet absorption spectra of anthracene derivatives. *Chem. Rev.* **1947**, *41* (2), 353–71.
- (55) Hoogenboom, R.; Thijs, H. M.; Jochems, M. J.; van Lankvelt, B. M.; Fijten, M. W.; Schubert, U. S. Tuning the LCST of poly(2-oxazoline)s by varying composition and molecular weight: alternatives to poly(N-isopropylacrylamide)? *Chem. Commun. (Camb)* **2008**, *44*, 5758–60.
- (56) Kim, J.; Beyer, V.; Becer, C. R. Poly(2-oxazoline) with Pendant Hydroxyl Groups via a Silyl Ether-Based Protecting Group. *Macromolecules* **2022**, *55* (23), 10651–10661.
- (57) Haladjova, E.; Rangelov, S.; Tsvetanov, C. Thermoresponsive Polyoxazolines as Vectors for Transfection of Nucleic Acids. *Polymers* **2020**, *12* (11), 2609.
- (58) Hoogenboom, R.; Thijs, H. M. L.; Wouters, D.; Hoepfener, S.; Schubert, U. S. Tuning solution polymer properties by binary -solvent mixtures. *Soft Matter* **2008**, *4* (1), 103–107.
- (59) Futscher, M. H.; Philipp, M.; Müller-Buschbaum, P.; Schulte, A. The Role of Backbone Hydration of Poly(N-isopropyl acrylamide) Across the Volume Phase Transition Compared to its Monomer. *Sci. Rep.* **2017**, *7* (1), 17012.

(60) Bahr, J. L.; Mickelson, E. T.; Bronikowski, M. J.; Smalley, R. E.; Tour, J. M. Dissolution of small diameter single-wall carbon nanotubes in organic solvents? *Chem. Commun.* **2001**, *2*, 193–194.

(61) Yang, M.-c.; Li, M.-y.; Luo, S.; Liang, R. Real-time monitoring of carbon nanotube dispersion using dynamic light scattering and UV-vis spectroscopy. *International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology* **2016**, *82* (1–4), 361–367.